

Minutes EB25-4
Meeting of the SeqCode Executive Board
26 November 2025 @ 7h00 (EST)

Attendance

Maria Chuvochina (MC)	- Chair, Reconciliation Commission
Phil Hugenholtz (PH)	- Member without portfolio
Kostas Konstantinidis (KK)	- Chair, Standards Working Group
Anna-Louise Reysenbach (ALR)	- Vice Chair
Luis Miguel Rodriguez (LMR)	- Chair, Registry Working Group
Iain Sutcliffe (IS)	- Chair, Legislative Commission
Fanus Venter (FV)	- Secretary
Barny Whitman (BW)	- Chair

Apologies

Fengping Wang (FW)	- Member without portfolio
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1. Welcome

BW welcomed the members of the Executive Board.

2. Additions to the Agenda

Resignation of Anna-Louise Reysenbach
Amendment of a SeqCode recommendation

3. Matters Arising/Action points from the previous meeting

New and ongoing action items from previous meeting

1. *FV to circulate the minutes of this meeting to the EB for their comments and approval and to alert the SeqCode Community once it is approved. Completed.*
2. *LMR and BW to prepare and submit a funding application for 2026 to the ISME office. Ongoing, this should be the last time an application is needed. ISME will provide support on an annual basis from 2027.*
3. *BW to prepare an updated manuscript to propose changes to the SeqCode. The updated SeqCode manuscript will be circulated and members are to respond by 15 September. Completed.*
4. *FV to request nominations for the vice-chair position as part of the next newsletter to the SeqCode community. Completed.*
5. *PH to request the ISME Board to allow ISME funding to be used as stipends to students. Permission obtained.*
6. *KK to ask the Standards Working Group to discuss possible minimum recommendations for metadata linked to entries. Completed.*
7. *FV to request ISME to consider waiving the publication costs of manuscripts related to the operation of the SeqCode in ISME Communications. Ongoing.*
8. *FV to request Bergey's Manual Trust to initiate the establishment of a representative organization committee for the proposed meeting between the ICSP and SeqCode. This discussion will be delayed until the new Executive of the ICSP has been elected.*

4. Reports from Commissions and Working Groups

Legislative Commission

A revised manuscript proposing amendments to the SeqCode, introducing the ability to designate strains as paratypes and amending the recommendations on name formation, has been resubmitted to ISME Communications. The public discussion of this proposal will be initiated in 2026 on the Slack channel once the manuscript has been accepted for publication.

Additional proposals to amend the SeqCode will be collected and combined in a proposal which will be prepared in 2026. This will include the recognition of the ranks of Domain and Kingdom.

Standards Working Group

The working group is in the process of providing minimum recommendations for metadata linked to entries of genome sequences. The board indicated that standard field and ontology should be used. KK, after consultation with LMR and the working group, will circulate suggestions to the board once the suggestion has been finalised.

The working group also decided that no additional quality requirements are currently required for genomes obtained from isolates.

Registry and Nomenclature Working Group

At present 1178 names have been validated, which include those of 636 species. LMR also indicated that the registry needs nomenclature support as there are nearly 2000 names currently under review.

Reconciliation Commission

At their meeting of 19 November 2025 the commission discussed the naming of species after friends or family as there is no rule to prohibit such practices. The proposed species name “*Anisomitus miae*” has therefor been validated for use. The board supported this decision and after some discussion decided that no rule needs to be introduced to prohibit this practice.

5. Election of new Vice-Chair

The board acknowledged the role ALR has played in the establishment of the SeqCode and thanked her for her support over the years of the committee’s existence and for her essential role in the committee’s founding. The only nomination received as Vice-Chair was for Marike Palmer. The election will be conducted in January. FV will contact the ISME office to ask for assistance with administering the ballot.

6. Legal protection of the SeqCode name

The EB agreed with the suggestion from LMR that we should look into protecting and securing the name and use of the SeqCode name. LMR was asked to investigate the possible options and processes to obtain legal protection for the SeqCode name.

7. Conference and Meeting Updates

EB members are encouraged to submit any relevant documents on the shared drive.

(https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1bH4Sluh3kjC9YM8CTqUn1T-q5c1kED7HvJLu_wNf2Pk/edit#gid=0)

New action items

1. FV to circulate the minutes of this meeting to the EB for their comments and approval and to alert the SeqCode Community once it is approved.
2. IS to initiate the discussion of the proposed changes to the SeqCode on the Slack channel once the manuscript has been accepted for publication.
3. KK to provide suggestion for minimum metadata recommendations for consideration by the board members.
4. FV to contact the ISME office to request assistance with the Vice-Chair voting process.
5. LMR to investigate the possible options and processes to obtain legal protection for the SeqCode name.

Ongoing items

6. LMR and BW to prepare and submit a funding application for 2026 to the ISME office.
7. FV to request ISME to consider waiving the publication costs of manuscripts related to the operation of the SeqCode in ISME Communications.

Minutes prepared by FV: 1 December 2025

Approved: 5 December 2025